

Synthesis of Biologically Active Compounds of Amino Ester Hydrochlorides derived from Substituted-cinchophen

K. M. DAOUD and M. N. IBRAHIM*

Department of Chemistry, College of Education, University of Mosul, Iraq
and

M. S. SAEED

Department of Chemistry, College of Science, University of Mosul, Iraq

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Syntheses of aminoethyl cinchoninate hydrochloride derivatives have been developed. The synthesis was based on the reaction of derivative of cinchoninyl chloride with *N*-hydroxyethyl derivatives of aliphatic and alicyclic amines. The structure of the products were assigned on the basis of their physical and spectral data.

THE anaesthetic property shown by compound 1 is attributed mainly to the dialkylaminoalkyl ester group. Since then many works proposed to achieve the synthesis of amino ester groups for many aromatic, alicyclic and heterocyclic compounds based mainly either by the reaction of the

acid chloride with dialkylaminoalkanol¹, or by the reaction of the acid with dialkylaminoalkyl chloride². In continuation of our work concerning the synthesis of dialkylaminoalkyl ester hydrochlorides derived from substituted cinchophen³, we report here the reaction of 8-chloro-2-(4-chlorophenyl)cinchoninyl chloride with *N*-hydroxyethyl derived from aromatic, alicyclic and aliphatic amines in an attempt to study how the anaesthetic properties would be affected by varying substituent at both cinchophen nucleus and aminoalkyl derivatives.

Experimental

IR spectra were recorded on Pye Unicam Sp-2000 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (deuteriopyridine) on a Bruker WH90 spectrometer with tetramethylsilane as the internal marker. Melting points were determined on a Kofler hot-plate and are uncorrected.

8-Chloro-2-(4-chlorophenyl)cinchoninic acid (1): The acid was prepared according to the reported

method⁴ and crystallised from ethanol, (60%), m.p. 267–68° (lit. 265–67°); ν_{max} 3 000 (OH acid), 1 700 (C=O) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (Ar).

8-Chloro-2-(4-chlorophenyl)cinchoninyl chloride (2): A mixture of the corresponding acid (1; 2.5 mol) and freshly distilled thionyl chloride (300 ml) refluxed for 6 h⁴ to yield the product, (88%), m.p. 158–60° (lit. 161–62°); ν_{max} 1 780 (COCl) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (Ar).

1-(2-Hydroxyethyl)amine derivatives (3): A mixture of 2-bromoethanol (25 g) and the corresponding amine (70 g) was heated at 80° for 72 h⁴ to afford the products as clear syrup (85%) whose physical data are similar to that described in the literature⁶.

General procedure for synthesis of 8-chloro-2-(4-chlorophenyl)-4-aminoethyl cinchoninate hydrochlorides (4a–h): To a solution of the acid chloride

Scheme 1. Reagent ; (i) Pyruvic acid.

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL AND NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p.* °C	δ (deuteropyridine)**
4a	62	211-12 ^a	2.55 (2H, t, CH ₂), 2.86 (4H, m, NCH ₂), 3.8 (4H, m, O(CH ₂) ₂), 4.25 (2H, t, CH ₂), 7.1-8.0 (7H, m, Ar), 8.30 (1H, s, Ar)
4b	60	192-94 ^b	1.35 (6H, m, (CH ₂) ₂), 2.6 (4H, t, N(CH ₂) ₂), 2.7 (2H, t, CH ₂), 4.12 (2H, t, CH ₂), 7.1-8.1 (7H, m, Ar) 8.31 (1H, s, Ar)
4c	60	186-88 ^a	1.11 (3H, d, CH ₃), 1.3-1.65 (6H, m, (CH ₂) ₂), 2.4 (2H, m, α_{ax}), 2.8 (2H, t, CH ₂), 3.1 (2H, m, α_{eq}), 4.0 (2H, t, CH ₂), 7.15-8.1 (7H, m, Ar), 8.34 (1H, s, Ar)
4d	62	175-77 ^a	1.0 (3H, d, CH ₃), 1.3-1.8 (5H, m, (CH ₂) ₂ CH), 2.85 (2H, t, CH ₂), 3.00 (2H, m, α_{ax}), 3.55 (2H, m, α_{eq}), 4.12 (2H, t, CH ₂), 7-7.95 (7H, m, Ar), 8.4 (1H, s, Ar)
4e	58	182-83 ^a	1.0 (3H, s, CH ₃), 1.5 (5H, m, (CH ₂) ₂ CH), 2.0 (2H, m, α_{ax}), 2.8 (2H, t, CH ₂), 3.1 (2H, m, α_{eq}), 4.0 (2H, t, CH ₂), 7.12-8.12 (7H, s, Ar), 8.4 (1H, s, Ar)
4f	50	178-80 ^b	2.65 (2H, t, CH ₂), 2.85 (6H, s, (CH ₂) ₂ N), 3.85 (2H, t, CH ₂), 7.12-7.8 (7H, m, Ar), 8.35 (1H, s, Ar)
4g	60	172-75 ^b	2.7 (2H, t, CH ₂), 4.0 (2H, t, CH ₂), 4.25 (4H, s, (CH ₂) ₂ Ph), 7.15-8.0 (17H, m, Ar), 8.32 (1H, s, Ar)
4h	52	177-79 ^a	2.81 (2H, t, CH ₂), 4.1 (2H, t, CH ₂), 7.15-8.15 (17H, m, Ar), 8.30 (1H, s, Ar)

*Solvent for crystallisation : ^aEtOH, ^bMeOH.

**Proton attached at α -position of alicyclic N-atom : α_{eq} = equatorial proton, α_{ax} = axial proton.

(2; 0.05 mol) in dry benzene (80 ml), was added the hydroxyamine derivatives (3; 0.05 mol) in benzene (80 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 30-40 min and the resulting solid formed after cooling was recrystallised from alcohol (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

8 Chloro-2-(4-chlorophenyl)cinchoninic acid was synthesised according to the Dohbner reaction⁷. The mechanism of the reaction involved in the first step is the formation of Schiff base which undergoes aldol type condensation with pyruvic acid to give after cyclisation and oxidation⁸ the corresponding acid (Scheme 1).

The acid is then converted to its acid chloride (2) which is isolated as free base after treatment with dry benzene.

In the last step of the synthesis⁹, the acid chloride (2) reacts with the corresponding *N*-hydroxyethylamine (3). The structural assignment of aminoethyl cinchoninate hydrochloride (4; Scheme 2) was achieved on the basis of its ir and nmr spectral data. The ir spectral data exhibit a strong band at 1750 cm⁻¹ due to ester carbonyl stretching. The nmr spectra for 4a-h are given in Table 1. The spectra exhibited characteristic two 2-H triplets for the ethylene group of the aminoethyl ester derivatives. The methylene protons adjacent to the N-atom appeared at low field due to their proximity to the heteroatom, while protons next to the oxygen atom of the ester group showed a signal at lower field than those of the N-CH₂ group, also the disappearance of the OH signal at δ 5.45 of the corresponding dialkylaminoethanol derivatives support the formation of compounds 4. The spectra of the aromatic protons showed downfield signals and characterised by AB quartet with coupling constant equal to *J* 6.0 Hz identified for *p*-chloro-substituted-phenyl part of the cinchophen nucleus. Other three-proton multiplet and one-proton singlet appear at downfield region of the spectra. The nmr spectra of alicyclic amine part of the compounds 4 was also studied (Table 1) and their interpretation was based on studying the spectra of some compounds containing saturated cyclic amine^{9,10}.

References

1. F. E. RAY and G. RIEVESHL, *J Am Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 836.
2. E. R. BOCKSTAHLER and D. L. WRIGHT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 3760.
3. M. S. SABED, M. N. IBRAHIM and A. M. JAMEL, *J. Univ. Kuwait (Sci.)*, 1989, 16, in the press.
4. R. E. LUTZ, *J. Am. Chem Soc*, 1946, 68, 1813.
5. C. F. BLICKE and E. L. JENNER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1722.
6. J. H. GARDNER and E. O. HAENNI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 2763.
7. O. DOEBNER, *Ann. Chem.*, 1887, 242, 265.
8. F. W. BERGSTROM, *Chem. Rev.*, 1944, 35, 156.
9. F. T. ABACHI, W. H. YOUSIF, N. M. AL-RAWI, A. M. KHODER and A. H. KHUTHIER, *J. Iraq Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 11, 105.
10. S. Y. HANNA, M.Sc. Thesis, University of Mosul, 1981.